

**EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS ON THE SELECTION OF FABRIC FOR
FILTRATION IN LABORATORY CONDITIONS**

Djamalov R.K.

Fiber Crop Research Institute

Hasanov H.A.

Termez State University of engineering and agrotechnologies

Abidovaa A.R.

Fiber Crop Research Institute

Annotation: The article presents the results of an experiment in which dust removal technologies that are separated from the cotton cleaning process are designed to remove fine impurities from the board and air, filter equipment for trapping fibrous materials, and filter fabrics are selected.

Keywords: filter, cloth, dust, cotton dust, fiber material, cleaning effect, fiber urine adhering to the surface of the fabric.

Аннотация. В статье представлен анализ технологий пылеочистки в процессе хлопкоочистки, про разработке фильтрующего оборудования для удаления мелких примесей из воздуха и результаты экспериментальных работ по выбору фильтровальных полотен.

Ключевые слова: фильтр, ткань, пыль, хлопковая пыль, волокнистый материал, очищающий эффект, удаление волокон с поверхности ткани.

Large-scale R & D work is being carried out in the world to improve the techniques, technology and their scientific basis for the initial processing of cotton. It is considered one of the important tasks in this direction, including improving atmospheric air and achieving energy-resource efficiency by effectively cleaning up fibrous materials that escape from the cotton content with dust. In this regard, in order to clean cotton dust in two stages and use filter devices in the second stage, it is

necessary to determine its parameters, determine the movement model of dust air in pipes and the technology of its purification.

At each stage of cotton ginning enterprises, there are specific pollinations, which are divided into mineral, organic and fiber.

At the technological stages of cotton processing plants, various types of powder smokers SP-6, SS-6, SL-3, SS-3, vzp-1200 and the like are being used [1, 2].

Dust grippers, operating through centrifugal force, generate centrifugal force by creating a circular motion of air in the body part of the gripper when separating the dust from the air. The body of such dust holders can be cylindrical, cylindrical-conical and conical in shape (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Scheme of centrifugal dust smokers.

A) cylinder; B) cone; V) cylinder-cone.

In cotton ginning enterprises, cylinder dust holders have been unused due to some disadvantages. This disadvantage is that increasing the number of air rotations as the airflow entering the cyclone moves in a circular motion based on centrifugal force causes the airflow to decrease in velocity, making it more difficult for dust particles to be delivered to the wall. Therefore, particles of dust moving in the cyclone cause the cleaning effect of the equipment to fall off without reaching the Wall [3].

A new filter equipment has been proposed to trap fibrous materials by purifying air separating from cyclones into the atmosphere [4]. The equipment is with input and output pipes, in the middle of which two drums are covered with filter fabric material, and a vacuum-Valve is installed to release waste, a rubber plank is installed on the bottom to remove residues from the fabric (Figure 2).

Filter equipment Body 1, inlet pipe 2, leading drum 3, soplo 4 for removing residues, tensioning drum 5, fabric material 6, vacuum valve 7, suction pipe 8, outlet pipe 9 and suction 10, rubber pad 11.

Figure 2. Scheme of the recommended filter equipment.

a) filter equipment, b) placement of a Caddo to remove residues from the filter fabric.

The filter equipment works as follows:

Polluted air enters the body 1 through the filter inlet pipe 2, which then passes through the outer and inner surface of the fabric material 6, as a suction 10 is installed in the airway, a rubber pad 11 is put on the urine tip so that the filter does not damage

the fabric and compacted with a vacuum-valve 7 at the bottom. The woven fabric material is cleaned in the air passage from 6, and the output pipe goes through 9 to the atmosphere.

With a built-in sopro 4 to remove dust residues from the inside of the material, and a vacuum valve 7 from the outside surface, the residues are transferred outside, the residues from sopro 4 are sucked through the suction pipe 8 into the fan and transmitted back to cleaning. Purified air is released into the atmosphere through the output pipe 9.

Thus, contaminated air is cleaned twice and brought to sanitary requirements.

In filters, it is mainly advisable if the fabric is selected based on the composition of the dust separating the filter elements from the equipment according to the types of production, since cotton dust is different from the dust of other products, it may contain more fiber materials. This fiber dust clings to the filter fabric and makes it difficult to separate from the fabric, so the choice of fabric is considered muxim.

During the filtration process, it is obtained that the equipment resistance is exceeded to ensure the continuous cleaning of the surface of the fabric, therefore, when cleaning the surface of the fabric, a built-in handle and a vacuum-Valve are used. The structure of the saplo is made so that when touching the fabric to urinate from above, the bottom is bent in the form of a groove to collect dust and draw air from the corridor (see Figure 2-b).

When conducting experiments, we first start with multi-used filter fabrics. A filter made of polyester was fitted and used and thus checked by installing sequentially obtained fabrics.

In the experiments, together with the determination of air permeability, the cleaning effect and the degree of purification of the surface of the fabric from fibrous

dust were determined, the results of the experiment are presented in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3. Effect of types of filtering fabrics on the effect of dust removal and the degree of separation of fibrous materials from the surface

It was decided to use artificial fabrics as it was observed that cotton dust was difficult to stick to the fabric and urinate from the surface of the fabric when it was obtained fabrics made of cotton and wool as a filtering fabric, and experiments were carried out on the choice of these fabrics.

The fabric chosen for filtering was installed on the stand and the dust prepared for the experiment was filtered for 120 seconds.

From the above histogram, it can be seen that when installing a “polyester” fabric for filtering, the cleaning effect was 92%, and the degree of cleaning of the fibrous material from the surface of the fabric was 99.5%. Among the selected filter fabrics, the cleaning effect of “Polyethylentereftalate” fabric was high, accounting for 97.6%, and the cleaning rate of fibrous material from the surface of the fabric was 99.5%. Therefore, the rest of the experiments are continued by preparing a fabric filter “Polyethylentereftalate”.

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